

PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING, STRESS LEVEL, TEACHING AND LEARNING DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS IN UBAY 1 DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the psychological well-being, stress levels, and teaching and learning development of 208 public elementary teachers in Ubay 1 District during the School Year 2023-2024. It further examined the relationships among these variables and identified differences based on teachers' profiles. A descriptive-quantitative correlational research design was employed using complete enumeration. Data were gathered through adapted survey questionnaires measuring psychological well-being, stress levels, and teaching and learning development. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and regression analyses were utilized. Findings revealed that teachers generally demonstrated positive psychological well-being, particularly in well-being and positivity, although some challenges in sleep and concentration were noted. Teachers experienced a moderate level of stress, with paperwork and administrative demands identified as major stressors. Meanwhile, teaching and learning development was rated as highly developed, especially in content knowledge and pedagogy. Significant relationships were found between psychological well-being, stress levels, and teaching and learning development, indicating that teachers' mental health plays a vital role in their instructional effectiveness. Based on the findings, an action plan was proposed to enhance teacher well-being and reduce stress, thereby improving teaching and learning outcomes.

Keywords: *Psychological well-being, Stress Levels, Teaching and Learning Development, Public Elementary School Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a vital role in delivering quality education, making their psychological well-being an essential factor in ensuring effective teaching and learning. In today's educational landscape, teachers face increasing demands, including diverse learner needs, administrative responsibilities, and evolving curriculum standards. These challenges contribute to heightened stress levels, which may affect both teacher performance and student outcomes. Research has emphasized that teaching is inherently a high-stress profession due to constant interpersonal interactions, accountability pressures, and workload demands (Fimian, M.J., 2016; Greenberg, M. T. & Brown, 2017). Preventive mental health approaches in schools further highlight the importance of supporting educators to sustain both personal well-being and professional effectiveness (Macklem, G. L., 2014).

Studies have shown that teachers' psychological well-being significantly influences their motivation, instructional practices, and classroom environment (Glazzard & Rose, 2020; Colli et al., 2012). Teachers who maintain positive mental health are more capable of managing stress, fostering student engagement, and implementing innovative teaching strategies. This aligns with findings that teacher well-being is closely linked to job satisfaction, resilience, and overall work performance (Benevene, P. et al., 2020). Moreover, social cognitive perspectives suggest that individuals' beliefs in their capabilities influence how they cope with challenges, including stress in professional settings (Beauchamp, M. R. et al., 2019). Teachers with strong self-efficacy and perceived support from administration are better able to manage job-related stress and maintain positive attitudes toward their students (Katsantonis, I. G., 2020).

Conversely, prolonged stress and poor mental health may lead to burnout, reduced job satisfaction, and diminished teaching effectiveness. From a behavioral perspective, environmental factors and reinforcement patterns also influence teacher responses to stress and workplace challenges (Ziafar, M. & Namaziandost, 2019). When stress is not properly addressed, it can negatively affect not only teachers but also students and the overall school climate. Thus, promoting teacher well-being is not only beneficial for educators but also essential for improving the quality of education.

In the Philippine context, mental health has become a priority, as reflected in Republic Act No. 11036 and Department of Education initiatives promoting mental health and psychological support services. Despite these efforts, many teachers continue to experience stress due to workload, limited resources, and emotional demands of teaching (Whiting et al., 2021).

In Ubay 1 District, concerns regarding stress, burnout, and psychological well-being among teachers highlight the need for further investigation. Understanding how psychological well-being and stress levels relate to teaching and learning development is crucial in designing interventions that support teachers and improve educational outcomes. Thus, this study examined the relationships among these variables and provided a basis for an action plan to enhance teacher well-being and instructional development.

Research Questions

The main goal of the study was to determine the psychological well-being and stress level to teaching and learning development of public elementary school teachers in Ubay I, Northeast District in the academic year 2023-2024. The findings served as the basis for crafting a proposed action plan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 designation;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.5 teaching experience?
2. What is the teacher's level of psychological well-being in terms of:
 - 2.1 sleep;
 - 2.2 well-being;
 - 2.3 emotion;
 - 2.4 positivity; and
 - 2.5 bouncing back?
3. What is the stress level of the teachers?
4. What is the teacher's level of teaching and learning development in terms of:
 - 4.1 content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 4.2 learning environment;
 - 4.3 diversity of learners, curriculum planning, assessment, and reporting; and
 - 4.4 community linkages?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the following:
 - 5.1 teacher's psychological well-being;
 - 5.2 stress level of the teachers; and
 - 5.3 level of teacher's teaching and learning development?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' teaching and learning development to their:
 - 6.1 psychological well-being; and
 - 6.2 level of stress?
7. Based on the findings, what action plan can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-quantitative correlational research design to examine the psychological well-being, stress levels, and teaching and learning development of public elementary school teachers in Ubay 1 District.

A total of 208 teachers from 16 public elementary schools participated in the study through complete enumeration. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire

consisting of four parts: respondents' profile, psychological well-being, stress levels, and teaching and learning development. The psychological well-being instrument included dimensions such as sleep, well-being, emotion, positivity, and resilience. Stress levels were measured using a 5-point Likert scale, while teaching and learning development covered content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, and community linkages. The instruments were adapted from existing studies and modified to suit the research context.

Prior to data collection, permission was secured from appropriate authorities, and respondents were informed of the purpose of the study. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality and anonymity were insured. Data were gathered through survey administration and were subsequently organized, analyzed, and interpreted.

Statistical tools used included frequency and percentage for demographic data, weighted mean for determining levels of variables, and regression analyses to identify relationships among psychological well-being, stress levels, and teaching and learning development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that the majority of teachers were female, held Teacher III positions, and had considerable teaching experience, indicating a stable and experienced workforce. A large proportion were also pursuing or had completed graduate studies, reflecting a commitment of professional growth.

In terms of psychological well-being, teachers generally demonstrated positive mental health. They reported a strong sense of purpose and life satisfaction, with well-being indicators occurring almost every day. Teachers also showed optimism and resilience, indicating their ability to cope with challenges. However, some concerns were noted in areas such as sleep quality and concentration, suggesting that certain aspects of mental health require attention. These findings support previous studies emphasizing the importance of mental well-being in enhancing teaching effectiveness and resilience (Liang et al., 2022).

Regarding stress levels, teachers experienced a moderate level of stress overall. Administrative workload, particularly excessive paperwork, emerged as the most significant stressor. Other contributors included classroom management challenges, large class-sizes and student-related concerns. These results align with existing literature highlighting workload and administrative demands as primary sources of teacher stress (Whiting et al., 2021; Richards et al., 2018). While stress levels were not extreme, they remain significant enough to impact teachers' well-being and performance if not properly addressed.

In terms of teaching and learning development, teachers were found to be highly developed, particularly in content knowledge and pedagogy. They demonstrated strong instructional competence, effective communication skills, and the ability to engage

learners. This indicates that despite experiencing moderate stress, teachers continue to perform effectively in their professional roles. These findings support the idea that professional development and experience contribute to teaching effectiveness (Cordingley, 2015).

Furthermore, the study found significant relationships between psychological well-being, stress levels, and teaching and learning development. Teachers with higher levels of psychological well-being tended to demonstrate better teaching performance, while higher stress levels were associated with potential challenges in instructional effectiveness. These results suggest that psychological well-being and stress are critical factors influencing teachers' professional performance. The findings reinforce the notion that supporting teachers' mental health can lead to improved teaching quality and better student outcomes.

Conclusions

Teachers generally demonstrate positive psychological well-being, moderate stress levels, and a high level of teaching and learning development. Psychological well-being and stress levels significantly influence teachers' instructional effectiveness. Teachers who maintain good mental health are more likely to perform effectively, while stress can hinder their performance if not properly managed. Therefore, promoting teacher well-being and reducing stress are essential in improving teaching and learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the implicated findings and conclusions, the researcher has drawn the following recommendations:

1. Teachers should empower themselves to prioritize their mental well-being and effectively manage their stress levels, which in turn would contribute to the progress of teaching and learning so that they will become proficient, efficient, and enthusiastic educators capable of nurturing well-rounded individuals who are globally competitive within the educational process.
2. Pupils should take into consideration teachers' psychological well-being, stress level, and teaching and learning development.
3. School heads should plan purposeful activities, topics, trainings, and workshops that would enhance teachers' psychological well-being, stress management, and teaching and learning development which could possibly help teachers in improving their teaching performance and professional growth.
4. DepEd Officials should provide additional information in planning and designing effective strategies for improving mental health, addressing stress levels, and teaching and learning development concerning globalization standards.
5. Future Researchers need to take possibilities on topics for further research on the mental health, stress level, and teaching and learning development of the school personnel.
6. A proposed action plan may be crafted and implemented.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were essential in this research to ensure integrity, accountability, trust, and fairness among all participants. In this study, the ethical treatment of teachers and school heads was given utmost importance. Their information remained confidential and anonymous, and the data collected were solely for academic purposes. Prior to participation, informed consent was secured, ensuring the respondents were fully aware of the objectives of the study and their role in it. Participation was voluntary, with the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without any negative consequence. Respondents were treated with dignity and respect, and the research was carried out impartially, without bias or external influence. The focus of the study remained on examining how distributed leadership supported collaborative school governance, and all findings were reported with fairness, accuracy, and academic honesty. The study complied with the guidelines established by the National Privacy Commission under the Data Privacy Act of 2012, ensuring adherence to data protection regulations. The researcher followed the Act's regulations and applied internationally recognized principles and standards to safeguard personal data. The research honored the fundamental human right to privacy while also promoting the free flow of knowledge for national progress and development. The researcher implemented all necessary measures to secure and protect personal data and information.

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